

The Reaction of Organocopper Reagents with Azobenzene, Azoxybenzene and *N*-Benzylideneamines

M. T. RAHMAN*, R. L. CHOWDHURY, M. A. QUADER and A. K. ROY

Department of Chemistry, University of Dhaka, Dhaka-2, Bangladesh

Manuscript received 12 March 1986, accepted 9 March 1987

Lithium diphenylcuprate reacts with azobenzene at -5° in THF for 2 h to give a dimetallic species which on hydrolysis gives hydrazobenzene (37%) or on benzoylation gives 1,2-dibenzoyl-1,2-diphenylhydrazine (31%). Magnesium-based cuprate reagents do not react with azobenzene under these conditions. Magnesium phenylcuprate, however, reduces azoxybenzene to azobenzene (50%), although the corresponding methylcuprate affords a near quantitative yield of azobenzene. Magnesium phenylcuprate does not react with benzylideneaniline or benzylidenebutylamine in THF for 4 h.

ORGANOCOPPER(I) reagents do not add to simple, isolated olefinic type of carbon-carbon double bonds^{1,2}, but they do so if the latter are activated by conjugation with aldehydic³⁻⁵, keto^{3,4}, ester^{3,4}, nitro^{6,7} or other olefinic⁸⁻¹⁰ groups giving 1,4-addition products. With acetylenic compounds no additional activation is required, however. The copper reagents add smoothly to both internal and terminal triple-bonds giving alkenylcopper reagents¹¹⁻¹⁴. Additionally, the organocopper reagents undergo conjugate addition to the carbon-carbon triple-bonds when the latter are conjugated with a carbonyl^{15,16}, nitrile¹⁷, sulphoxide¹⁸ or sulphone¹⁹ groups. Contrary to the earlier contention¹⁻³, organocopper reagents, under certain conditions, add to the carbon-oxygen double bonds of *C*-nitroso²³, *O*-nitroso²³ and *N*-nitroso²⁴ compounds. However, to date no reactions of organocopper reagents with compounds containing $-N=N-$, $-N=N(O)-$ and $-C=N-$ groups have been reported. We report herein some of these reactions.

Experimental

All reactions were carried out under a positive pressure of dry, oxygen-free nitrogen. The ethereal solvents were dried over sodium wire and distilled from sodium benzophenone ketyl prior to use.

Reaction of lithium diphenylcuprate with azobenzene: To lithium diphenylcuprate (prepared from phenyllithium, 0.04 mol, and copper(I) iodide 0.02 mol, in 100 ml of THF at -10° for 1 h) was added dropwise a solution of azobenzene (0.01 mol) in THF (10 ml) over a period of 25 min and the mixture was stirred at -5° for 2 h. The mixture was then hydrolysed by ammonia solution, saturated with ammonium chloride, and the organic

matter was extracted in ether and the ether-extract dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Concentration of this ether solution gave crystals of hydrazobenzene (37%) which was washed with chilled ether-petroleum ether (b.p. $40-60^{\circ}$) (1:1 mixture) and its identity was established by comparing its m.p. and ir spectra with those of an authentic sample. The mother-liquor contained biphenyl and unreacted azobenzene (tlc) and the mixture was separated by column chromatography (silica gel; using petroleum ether, b.p. $40-60^{\circ}$ and then benzene-petroleum ether mixture as the eluants). The yields of biphenyl and azobenzene were 24 and 50%, respectively. The substances were characterised by tlc and by comparing their m.p.s. and ir spectra with those of authentic specimens.

In another run under similar conditions, instead of hydrolysing the reaction mixture, it was derivatised by adding benzoyl chloride (0.02 mol) in THF (25 ml) and stirring the resultant mixture at 0° for 2 h and then at the reflux temperature of THF for 1 h. The reaction mixture was hydrolysed with aqueous ammonia, saturated with ammonium chloride, and then extracted with ether (3×50 ml). The combined ether extract was washed several times with aqueous ammonia-ammonium chloride solution until the blue colour of the copper complex disappeared. The ether extract was then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and the solvent removed from the filtrate to give a brown solid. Column chromatographic separation (silica gel column, petroleum ether, b.p. $40-60^{\circ}$, and then benzene as eluants) gave biphenyl (25%), azobenzene (50%), benzophenone (50%) (based on the starting amount of benzoyl chloride) and finally, 1,2-dibenzoyl-1,2-diphenylhydrazine (31%), m.p. $158-59^{\circ}$ (rectified spirit) (lit.²⁵ 160°); ν_{max} (KBr) 3076w, 3050w, 3020w, 1979w, 1954w, 1895w, 1810w, 1770w,

1 665br vs, 1 588s, 1 576s, 1 485vs, 1 444vs, 1 320-1 260vs br, 1 181m, 1 152m, 1 105m, 1 070m, 1 025s, 1 000s, 796s, 770s, 766s, 740s, 723s and 695vs cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3 solution, TMS) 7.55-7.20 (m, ArH); m/e (70 eV) 392 (M^+), 287 ($\text{M}-\text{PhCO}^+$), 196 (PhNCO^+), 182 ($\text{M}-2\text{PhCO}^+$), 105 (PhCO^+), 91 (PhN^+) and 77 (Ph^+).

Reaction of phenylmagnesium bromide with azobenzene: To phenylmagnesium bromide (0.02 mol) in diethyl ether (100 ml) was added a solution of azobenzene (0.01 mol) in ether (50 ml) during 30 min. After refluxing the mixture for 8 h, benzoyl chloride (0.02 mol) in ether (50 ml) was added to it over a period of 30 min. When the vigour of the exothermic reaction decreased, it was refluxed for 3 h, allowed to stand overnight, hydrolysed with saturated $\text{NH}_3-\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ solution and then the organic matter was collected in ether (3×50 ml). The combined ether extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and the ether solution concentrated. The precipitated crystalline mass was separated by filtration, recrystallised from rectified spirit and dried to give 1,2-dibenzoyl-1,2-diphenylhydrazine (45%), m.p. 158-59°. By following the same separation technique as before, from the mother-liquor, biphenyl (71%), azobenzene (6%) and benzanilide (10%) were isolated and characterised.

Reaction of magnesium phenylcuprate with azobenzene: To a cooled (-10°) preparation of magnesium phenylcuprate (from 0.04 mol of phenylmagnesium bromide, 0.02 mol of copper(I) iodide in 100 ml of THF at -5° for 3 h) azobenzene (0.01 mol) dissolved in THF (50 ml) was added during 25 min, and the mixture was stirred at -5° for 2 h. Benzoyl chloride (0.02 mol) dissolved in THF (25 ml) was then added and the mixture stirred for 2 h at 0° and refluxed for 1 h. The reaction mixture was hydrolysed with saturated $\text{NH}_3-\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ solution and worked up as before to give biphenyl (16%), benzophenone (78%) and azobenzene (94%). 1,2-Dibenzoyl-1,2-diphenylhydrazine was not formed. When the above reaction was carried out in diethyl ether rather than in THF, the yields of biphenyl, benzophenone and azobenzene were 16, 55 and 91%, respectively; and the bisbenzoyl derivative was (tlc).

Reaction of polymeric phenylcopper reagent with azobenzene: When the above sequence of reactions was carried out with polymeric phenylcopper reagent (prepared from 0.025 mol phenylmagnesium bromide and 0.025 mol copper(I) iodide in 100 ml THF, at -5° for 3 h) and azobenzene (0.025 mol) worked up in the same way as above, the formation of no hydrazine or 1,2-dibenzoyl-1,2-diphenylhydrazine was detected (by tlc). A substantial quantity of biphenyl, and azobenzene (90%) were obtained.

Reaction of magnesium methylcuprate with azobenzene in presence of HMPA: To magnesium

methylcuprate (prepared from 0.04 mol of methylmagnesium iodide and 0.02 mol of copper(I) iodide in 100 ml of ether at -10°) HMPA (10 ml) was added and the mixture stirred to give a dense yellow solution. Azobenzene (0.01 mol) was then added all at a time, and the mixture stirred at 0 to -5° for 2 h and refluxed for 1 h. Benzoyl chloride (0.02 mol) in ether (25 ml) was then added dropwise to the reaction mixture whose colour rapidly turned deep red. The mixture was refluxed for 3 h, hydrolysed with saturated aqueous $\text{NH}_3-\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ solution and worked up in the usual way to give acetophenone (39%) and azobenzene (96%).

Reaction of magnesium phenylcuprate with azoxybenzene: To a preparation of magnesium phenylcuprate (from 0.04 mol phenylmagnesium bromide and 0.02 mol copper(I) iodide in 100 ml diethyl ether at -5° for 3 h) was added azoxybenzene (0.01 mol) all at a time, and the mixture stirred at -5° for 1 h and then at 0° for 2 h. The usual work up gave biphenyl (27%), azobenzene (45%) and azoxybenzene (51%).

Reaction of magnesium methylcuprate with azoxybenzene: To magnesium methylcuprate (prepared from 0.08 mol methylmagnesium iodide in 50 ml of ether and 0.04 mol copper(I) iodide in 50 ml of THF at -5° for 3 h) was added azoxybenzene (0.01 mol) dissolved in THF (10 ml). The colour of the reaction mixture turned greenish and a vigorous evolution of gas took place. The mixture was stirred at 0° for 0.5 h and then at room temperature for 3.5 h and finally refluxed for 0.5 h. The progress of the reaction was followed by tlc. The usual work up afforded azobenzene (97%) of high purity, m.p. 67-8° (lit.²⁶ 67-8°).

Reaction of magnesium phenylcuprate with *N*-benzylideneaniline and *N*-benzylidenebutylamine: Magnesium phenylcuprate (prepared from 0.02 mol phenylmagnesium bromide and 0.01 mol copper(I) iodide in 100 ml of THF at -5° for 3 h) and *N*-benzylideneaniline (0.005 mol) were stirred at 0° for 4 h and then worked up in the usual way to give back *N*-benzylideneaniline (95%). No other products were detected (tlc). No other products were obtained either when *N*-benzylidenebutylamine was used in the above reaction instead of *N*-benzylideneaniline.

Results and Discussion

Reaction with azobenzene: Lithium diphenylcuprate reacts with azobenzene at -5° for 2 h to give, subsequent to hydrolytic work up, 1,2-diphenylhydrazine and biphenyl in 37 and 24% yields, respectively. Some 50% of the azobenzene was recovered. If instead of hydrolysis, benzoyl chloride was added to the reaction mixture and allowed to react for 2 h at 0° , 1,2-dibenzoyl-1,2-diphenylhydrazine is obtained in 31% yield along with biphenyl (25%), benzophenone (50%) and azobenzene (50%). These results may be explained on assuming that

RAHMAN, CHOWDHURY, QUADER & ROY : THE REACTION OF ORGANOCOPPER REAGENTS *etc.*

5. A. HAMON, B. LACOUME, A. OLIVIER and W. R. PILGRIN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1975, 4481.
6. A. T. HANSSON and M. NILSSON, *Tetrahedron*, 1982, 38, 389.
7. N. ONO, I. HAMAMOTO and A. KAJI, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1984, 5, 274; S. STIVIER and P. YATES, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1983, 1, 50.
8. J. F. NORMANT, G. CAHIEZ and J. VILLIERAS, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1975, 92, C28.
9. H. KLEIJN, H. WESTMIJZE, A. SCHAAP, H. J. T. BOS and P. VERMEER, *Rec. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas*, 1979, 98, 209; F. NAEF, R. DECORZANT and S. D. ESCHER, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1982, 23, 5043.
10. A. I. PEARSON, S. H. KOLE and B. CHEM, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 105, 4483; B. R. DAVIS and S. J. JOHNSON, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1979, 2840.
11. J. F. NORMANT and M. BOURGAIN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1971, 2583; A. ALEXAKIS, J. F. NORMANT and J. VILLIERAS, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1975, 96, 471.
12. C. GERMON, A. ALEXAKIS and J. F. NORMANT, *Synthesis*, 1984, 40; M. GARDETTE, A. ALEXAKIS and J. F. NORMANT, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1982, 23, 5155.
13. I. FLEMING, T. T. NEWTON and F. ROESSLER, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1981, 2527.
14. M. OBAYSHI, K. UJIMOTO and H. NOZAKI, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1979, 177, 145.
15. E. J. COREY and J. A. KATZENELLENBOGEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 91, 1851.
16. J. B. SIDDALL, M. BISKUP and J. H. FRIED, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 91, 1853.
17. H. WESTMIJZE, H. KLEIJN and P. VERMEER, *Synthesis*, 1978, 454.
18. W. E. TRUCE and M. L. LUSCH, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1978, 43, 2252.
19. V. FIANDONESE, G. MARCHESI and F. NASO, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1978, 5131.
20. A. ALEXAKIS and J. F. NORMANT, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1982, 23, 5151.
21. J. P. MARINO and R. J. LINDERMAN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1983, 48, 4621; J. P. MARINO and M. D. FLOYD, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1975, 3897.
22. M. BOURGAIN-COMMERCON, J. P. FOULON and J. F. NORMANT, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1982, 228, 321.
23. M. T. RAHMAN, A. K. ROY and K. M. HOSSAIN, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1977, 127, 105.
24. M. T. RAHMAN, I. ARA and A. F. M. SALAHUDDIN, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1976, 959.
25. FREUNDLER, *Compt. Rend.*, 1903, 136, 1553.
26. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, London, 1956, p. 631.
27. H. GILMAN and R. M. PICKENS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 2405.
28. M. T. RAHMAN, A. K. M. M. HOQUE, I. SIDDIQUE, D. A. N. CHOWDHURY, S. K. NAHAR and S. L. SAHA, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1980, 188, 293.
29. M. S. KHARASCH and O. REINMUTH, "Grignard Reactions of Non-metallic Substances", 1st. ed., Prentice Hall, New York, 1954, p. 1236.